

ISSN (E): 2277-7695
ISSN (P): 2349-8242
NAAS Rating: 5.23
TPI 2022; 11(8): 1713-1715
© 2022 TPI
www.thepharmajournal.com
Received: 29-05-2022
Accepted: 10-07-2022

NVS Supriya
PG Scholar, Department of Fruit Science, College of Horticulture, Dr. YSR Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, West Godavari, Andhra Pradesh, India

M Madhavi
Associate Dean, Professor & Head, Department of Fruit Science, College of Horticulture, Dr. YSR Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, West Godavari, Andhra Pradesh, India

P Vinaya Kumar Reddy
Assistant Professor, Department of Fruit Science, College of Horticulture, Dr. YSR Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, West Godavari, Andhra Pradesh, India

P Subbramma
Associate Professor, Department Plant physiology, College of Horticulture, Dr. YSR Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, West Godavari, Andhra Pradesh, India

P Rama Devi
Professor, Department of Plant pathology, College of Horticulture, Dr. YSR Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, West Godavari, Andhra Pradesh, India

Corresponding Author:
NVS Supriya
PG Scholar, Department of Fruit Science, College of Horticulture, Dr. YSR Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, West Godavari, Andhra Pradesh, India

Effect of AM fungi on growth of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) seedlings

NVS Supriya, M Madhavi, P Vinaya Kumar Reddy, P Subbramma and P Rama Devi

Abstract

The present investigation entitled “Effect of AM fungi on growth of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) Seedlings” was carried out during December 2021 to May 2022 at center of excellence for protected cultivation (CEPC), Dr. Y.S.R Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, West Godavari. The experiment was laid out in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four treatments *Glomus fasciculatum* @ 3 g, *Glomus leptotichum* @ 3 g, *Glomus fasciculatum* @ 1.5 g + *Glomus leptotichum* @ 1.5 g, non mycorrhizal) and five replication. The results revealed that the application of *Glomus fasciculatum* @ 1.5 g+ *Glomus leptotichum* @ 1.5 g resulted in significant improvement of seedling height (19.27, 27.61, 38.98, 45.67 and 53.17 cm), number of leaves per seedling (11.88, 16.38, 19.23, 22.34 and 25.12), stem diameter (3.65, 4.42, 4.85, 5.45 and 6.13 mm) and total chlorophyll content (8.91, 9.56, 10.74, 11.00 and 12.16 mg/g⁻¹) at 70, 90, 110, 130, 150 days after sowing.

Keywords: Custard apple, AM fungi, Seedling height, number of leaves, stem diameter, total chlorophyll

Introduction

Custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) is an important minor fruit crop grown under tropical and sub tropical climatic conditions. The main commercial species of the genus *Annona* are *A. cherimola* Mill, *A. squamosa* L, *A. muricata* L, *A. reticulata* and *A. glabra*. The symbiosis of mycorrhizal fungi with plant roots has been linked to increased plant growth and development (Hall, 1988) [7], and increased P contents in tissues (Johnson & Hummel, 1985) [8]. VA mycorrhizas can increase the drought resistance of host plants (Nelson and Safir, 1985) [12]. Hitherto several mechanisms have been proposed to explain drought protection by AMF, such as changes in plant hormones levels (Goicoechea *et al.*, 1995) [6], increased photosynthesis (RuizLozano *et al.*, 1996), enhanced activity of enzymes involved in anti-oxidant defense (RuizLozano *et al.*, 1996), enhanced water uptake through improved hydraulic conductivity and increase in leaf conductance and photosynthetic activity (Amico *et al.*, 2002) [5], osmotic adjustment and changes in cell-wall elasticity (Auge *et al.*, 1987) [1].

By keeping the above aspects in view, the investigations were undertaken to study the effect of AM fungi *viz.*, *Glomus fasciculatum* and *Glomus leptotichum* on growth of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) seedlings.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation entitled “Effect of AM fungi on growth of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) Seedlings” was carried out during December 2021 to May 2022 at center of excellence for protected cultivation (CEPC), Dr. Y.S.R Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, West Godavari. The experiment was laid out in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four treatments *Glomus fasciculatum* @ 3 g, *Glomus leptotichum* @ 3 g, *Glomus fasciculatum* @ 1.5 g+*Glomus leptotichum* @ 1.5 g and non mycorrhizal) and five replications. Potting mixture used comprises of 2:1:1 ratio of red earth soil, FYM and vermicompost. They are mixed well and sterilized in autoclave for 15 minutes at 121 °C and 15 psi pressure. Polythene bags of 20 cm × 17 cm size and 300-gauge thickness were used for filling the potting mixture after surface sterilization with 1% formaldehyde. AM fungi was inoculated in poly bags before sowing of seed. Five seedlings were randomly selected and tagged in each replication for recording the non-destructive observations on shoot parameters throughout the study (at 70, 90, 110, 130 and 150 DAS) in polybag. For total chlorophyll content (mg/g⁻¹ fresh weight) four fresh leaves from middle part of seedling

region in each treatment were plucked on 70, 90, 110, 130 and 150 days after sowing for estimating chlorophyll content. The chlorophyll content was estimated as per the procedure outlined by Arnon (1949) [17]. The collected fresh leaves are macerated with 80% acetone and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes then O.D values are taken at wave lengths of 645 and 663 nm using spectrophotometer.

Total chlorophyll is calculated based on the following formula.

$$\text{Total chlorophyll mg/g}^{-1}\text{tissue} = [20.2(A_{645}) - 8.02(A_{663})] \times V / 1000 \times W$$

where,

A = Absorbance of specific wave lengths (645 and 663 nm)

V = Final volume of chlorophyll extractant in 80 per cent acetone in 100 ml.

W = Fresh weight of leaf sample (1 g)

Results and Discussion

The data pertaining to custard apple seedling height(cm) from table 1 revealed that significant maximum height of seedling (19.27, 27.61, 38.98, 45.67 and 53.17) were recorded in T3 (*Glomus fasciculatum* @ 1.5 g + *Glomus leptotichum* @ 1.5 g) followed by T1 (*Glomus fasciculatum* @ 1.5g) with 18.14, 24.68, 33.65, 39.90 and 45.35 where as minimum height of seedling (13.35, 18.58, 22.89, 28.45 and 33.89) were registered in T4 (non mycorrhizal) at 70, 90, 110, 130 and 150 DAS respectively. Increase in height of seedlings might be attributed due to synthesis of beneficial hormones by AM fungi which results in increase in cell division and cell multiplication. (Miller, 1971 [10], Crafts and Miller, 1974 [4], and Slankis, 1975. The results are in harmony with the findings of Rupnawar and Navale, 2000 [16] in pomegranate and Ojha *et al.*, 2008 in custard apple seedlings.

Number of leaves per seedling

From the data on number of leaves produced in table 2 it is evident that irrespective of the treatments imposed, the number of leaves produced per seedling increased during the period of study *i.e.* up to 150 DAS. However, due to influence of AM fungi the number of leaves produced per seedling differed significantly. Highest number of leaves (11.88, 16.38, 19.23, 22.34 and 25.12) were produced in T3 (*Glomus fasciculatum*@ 1.5 g + *Glomus leptotichum* @ 1.5 g) followed by T2 (*Glomus leptotichum* @ 3 g) with 10.72, 14.74, 16.98, 20.89 and 22.13 whereas lowest number of leaves (8.48,

12.67, 15.12, 17.98 and 19.78) were observed in T4 (non mycorrhizal) at 70, 90, 110, 130 and 150 DAS respectively. The absorption and mobilization of nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, copper, boron, zinc, sulphur and maintenance of soil moisture around the plant roots by AM fungi might be responsible for the production of more leaves in AM fungi treated seedling (Mosse *et al.*, 1981) [11]. A similar effect of AM fungi on number of leaves was also reported by Reena and Bagyraj (1990) [14] in tamarind and Rupnawar and Navale (2000) [16] in orange.

Stem diameter (mm)

The data depicted in table 3 and showed maximum stem diameter (mm) (3.65, 4.42, 4.85, 5.45 and 6.13) in T3 (*Glomus fasciculatum* @ 1.5 g + *Glomus leptotichum* @ 1.5 g) followed by T2 (*Glomus leptotichum*) with 3.12, 4.06, 4.45, 5.01 and 5.87 whereas minimum stem diameter (2.25, 2.90, 3.34, 3.89 and 4.04) was found in T4 (non mycorrhizal) at 70, 90, 110, 130 and 150 DAS respectively. Increase in stem diameter in AM inoculated treatments might be due to increase in availability of macro and micro nutrients, which helps in production of more number of photosynthetically active leaves which in turn helps in development of better stem diameter (Borah *et al.*, 1994) [3]. Similar findings were reported in sweet orange cv. mosambi (Singh *et al.*, 2000).

Total chlorophyll (mg/g⁻¹ fresh weight)

From the data presented in table 4 it is evident that total chlorophyll (mg/g-1 fresh weight) content per seedling increased with increase in days after sowing in all the treatments however chlorophyll content differed significantly among the treatments. Maximum chlorophyll content (8.91, 9.56, 10.74, 11.00 and 12.16) were recorded in T3 (*Glomus fasciculatum* @ 1.5 g + *Glomus leptotichum* @ 1.5 g) followed by T2 (*Glomus leptotichum*) with 8.32, 9.47, 10.07, 10.43 and 10.84 and minimum chlorophyll content (6.75, 7.89, 8.50, 9.09, 9.74) were reported in T4 (non mycorrhizal) at 70, 90, 110, 130 and 150 DAS respectively. Enhanced total chlorophyll content in AM fungi inoculated seedlings might be due to the direct effect of symbiotic association between host and AM fungi which led to higher water and nutrient uptake thereby results in higher biosynthesis of chlorophyll. AM fungi induced nitrogen uptake may increase chlorophyll content in inoculated seedling. The present results are in accordance with the findings of Manoharan *et al.* (2010) [9] in *Erythrina variegata*.

Table 1: Influence of AM Fungi on seedling height (cm) in custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.)

Treatment	Seedling height (cm)				
	70 DAS	90 DAS	110 DAS	130 DAS	150 DAS
T ₁ (<i>G. fasciculatum</i> @ 3g)	18.14	24.68	33.65	39.90	45.35
T ₂ (<i>G. leptotichum</i> @ 3g)	17.09	22.93	30.03	36.87	42.78
T ₃ (<i>G. fasciculatum</i> @ 1.5 g + <i>G. leptotichum</i> @ 1.5 g)	19.27	27.61	38.98	45.67	53.17
T ₄ (Non mycorrhizal)	13.35	18.58	22.89	28.45	33.89
SE(m) ±	0.09	0.14	0.25	0.24	0.32
CD at 5%	0.29	0.42	0.75	0.73	0.96

Table 2: Influence of AM Fungi on number of leaves per seedling in custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.)

Treatment	Number of Leaves				
	70 DAS	90 DAS	110 DAS	130 DAS	150 DAS
T ₁ (<i>G. fasciculatum</i> @ 3 g)	10.42	14.56	16.85	19.58	21.89
T ₂ (<i>G. leptotichum</i> @ 3 g)	10.72	14.74	16.98	20.89	22.13
T ₃ (<i>G. fasciculatum</i> @ 1.5 g + <i>G. leptotichum</i> @ 1.5 g)	11.88	16.38	19.23	22.34	25.12
T ₄ (Non mycorrhizal)	8.48	12.67	15.12	17.98	19.78
SE(m) ±	0.47	0.43	0.21	0.23	0.27
CD at 5%	1.42	1.32	0.63	0.70	0.81

Table 3: Influence of AM Fungi on stem diameter (mm) in custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) seedlings.

Treatment	Stem diameter(mm)				
	70 DAS	90 DAS	110 DAS	130 DAS	150 DAS
T ₁ (<i>G. fasciculatum</i> @ 3 g)	3.04	3.75	4.09	4.56	4.99
T ₂ (<i>G. leptotichum</i> @ 3 g)	3.12	4.06	4.45	5.01	5.87
T ₃ (<i>G. fasciculatum</i> @ 1.5 g + <i>G. leptotichum</i> @ 1.5 g)	3.65	4.42	4.85	5.45	6.13
T ₄ (Non mycorrhizal)	2.25	2.90	3.34	3.89	4.04
SE(m) ±	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04
CD at 5%	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.11

Table 4: Influence of AM Fungi on chlorophyll content in custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) seedlings.

Treatment	Chlorophyll content (mg/g ⁻¹)				
	70 DAS	90 DAS	110 DAS	130 DAS	150 DAS
<i>G. fasciculatum</i> @ 3 g	8.23	9.35	9.98	10.12	10.81
<i>G. leptotichum</i> @ 3 g	8.32	9.47	10.07	10.43	10.84
<i>G. fasciculatum</i> @ 1.5 g + <i>G. leptotichum</i> @ 1.5 g	8.91	9.56	10.74	11.00	12.16
Non mycorrhizal	6.75	7.89	8.50	9.09	9.74
SE(m) ±	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.11	0.28
C.D.	0.19	0.22	0.29	0.33	0.86

Conclusion

The present investigation on the effect of AM fungi on seedling growth of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) revealed that combined application of AM fungi species *i.e.* *Glomus fasciculatum* @ 1.5 g + *Glomus leptotichum* @ 1.5 g followed by application of AM fungi species *Glomus leptotichum* @ 3 g alone showed superior performance in terms of growth parameters. The results indicated the positive effect of AM fungi on growth of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) seedlings.

References

- Auge RM, Schekel KA, Wanple RL. Rose leaf elasticity changes in response to mycorrhizal colonization and drought acclimation. *Physiologia plantarum*. 1987;70(2):175-182.
- Azcon A, Bago B. Physiological characteristics of the host plant promoting an undisturbed functioning of the mycorrhizal symbiosis. Impact of Arbuscular Mycorrhizas on Sustainable Agriculture and Natural Ecosystems. 1994;3(1):47-60.
- Borah AS, Nath A, Ray AK, Bhat R, Maheswarappa HP, Subramanian P, *et al.* Effect of seed size, rooting medium and fertilizers on the growth of seedlings of silk cotton (*Ceiba pentandra* Linn.). *Indian Journal of Forestry*. 1994;17(4):293-300.
- Crafts CB, Miller CO. Detection and identification of cytokinins produced by mycorrhizal fungi. *Plant Physiology*. 1974;54(1):586-588.
- Amico JD, Torrecillas A, Rodriguez P, Morte A, Sanchezblanco MJ. Responses of tomato plants associated with the arbuscular mycorrhizal fungus *Glomus clarum* during drought and recovery. *Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. 2002;138(4):387-393.
- Goicoechea N, Antolin MC, Sanchez-diaz M. Gas exchange is related to the hormone balance in mycorrhizal or nitrogen-fixing alfalfa subjected to drought. *Physiology of Plantae*. 1997;100(2):989-97.
- Hall TJ. Pasture species are suitable for revegetating degraded granitic soils of Hervey Range military training area in North Queensland. *Tropical Grassland*. 1988;22(2):68-72.
- Johnson CR, Hummel RL. Influence of mycorrhizae and drought stress on growth of poncirus x citrus seedlings. *Horticultural Science*. 1985;20(1):754-55.
- Manoharan PT, Shanmugaiah V, Balasubramanian N, Gomathinayagam S, Sharma MP, Muthuchelian, K. Influence of AM fungi on the growth and physiological status of *Erythrina variegata* Linn. Grown under different water stress conditions. *European Journal of Soil Biology*. 2010;46(5):151-56.
- Miller CO. Cytokinin production by mycorrhizal fungi. *Mycorrhizae*. 1971;3(2):168-174.
- Mosse B. Advances in study of vesicular arbuscular mycorrhiza. *Annual Review of Phytopathology*. 1981;11(1):171-198.
- Nelson CE, Safir GR. Increased drought tolerance of mycorrhizal onion plants caused by improved phosphorus nutrition. *Plantae Scientia*. 1982;154(2):407-13.
- Ojha S, Chakraborty MR, Chakrabarti J, Chatterjee NC. Fruit-rot of custard apple (*Annona squamosa*) - a new disease from Burdwan, West Bengal. *Journal Mycopathological Research*. 2005;43(1):143-144.
- Reena J, Bagyaraj DJ. Growth stimulation of *Tamarindus indica* by selected VA-mycorrhizal fungi. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*. 1990;6(1):59-63.
- RuizLozano JM, Azcon R, Gomez M. Effects of arbuscular mycorrhizal *Glomus* species on drought tolerance: physiological and nutritional plant responses. *Applied Environment Microbiology*. 1995;61(2):456-60.
- Rupnawar BS, Navale AM. Effect of VA-mycorrhizal inoculation on growth of pomegranate layers. *Journal of Maharashtra Agricultural University*. 2000;25(1):44-46.
- Arnon DI. Copper enzymes in isolated chloroplasts and polyphenoloxidase in *Beta vulgaris*. *Plant Physiology*. 1949;24(1):1-15.